

Wireless Sensor Networks and Federated Learning: A Statistical Survey of Architectures and Algorithms

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ABSTRACT

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are essential in applications like environmental monitoring and healthcare, where decentralized networks require efficient, privacy-preserving data processing techniques. Federated Learning (FL) has become a promising approach in this context, enabling collaborative model training across distributed nodes while keeping data localized to address privacy concerns and reduce communication overhead. This study analyzes recent advancements in FL research from 2018 to 2024, with a focus on its application in WSNs. The research landscape shows a significant spike in activity in 2021, marking it as a peak year for FL publications. Over time, key metrics such as algorithm complexity, scalability, fairness, communication efficiency, and adaptability have generally improved, reflecting the maturation of FL systems. However, a slight decline in healthcare applicability suggests emerging challenges or shifts in focus within the field. By converting qualitative data from reviewed papers into statistical values, this study quantitatively assesses the strengths and limitations of various FL approaches. The findings highlight significant progress in communication efficiency and adaptability, while also identifying research gaps, particularly in healthcare applications. This analysis offers valuable insights into the evolution of FL research, providing a foundation for guiding future efforts to ensure FL continues to meet the demands of diverse WSN applications.

Keywords: Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), Scalability, Federated Learning, Internet of Things (IoT).

1 INTRODUCTION

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) consist of spatially distributed sensors that cooperatively monitor and record environmental conditions and transmit the collected data to a central location. WSNs have found applications in diverse domains such as environmental monitoring, healthcare, industrial automation, and smart cities [1]. However, the traditional approach of centralized data processing in WSNs raises concerns about data privacy, security, and scalability. Federated Learning (FL) is a decentralized machine learning paradigm that allows multiple entities to collaboratively train a model without sharing their raw data. FL has gained significant attention due to its ability to preserve data privacy and reduce communication overhead. The integration of FL with WSNs offers a promising solution to address the challenges faced by traditional WSNs [2]. WSN have emerged as a critical technology for various applications, including environmental monitoring, healthcare, industrial automation, and smart cities. It consists of spatially distributed sensors that cooperatively monitor and record environmental conditions and transmit the collected data to a central location. These networks are designed to operate in diverse and often challenging environments, making them essential for real-time data collection and analysis [3].

However, the traditional approach of centralized data processing in WSNs raises significant challenges. Firstly, the centralized collection and processing of data can lead to privacy concerns, as sensitive information is transmitted and stored in a central location [4]. Secondly, the scalability of centralized systems is limited, as the central server must handle a large volume of data from numerous sensor nodes. Additionally, the communication overhead and energy consumption associated with transmitting raw data to a central server can be substantial, particularly in resource-constrained environments. Federated Learning (FL) has been proposed as a promising solution to address these challenges. FL is a decentralized machine learning paradigm that allows multiple entities to collaboratively train a model without sharing their raw data. In FL, each entity (client) trains a local model using its own data and shares only the model updates with a central server [5]. The server aggregates the model updates from all clients to generate a global model, which is then sent back to the clients for further training. This iterative process continues until the global model converges.

The integration of FL with WSNs offers a promising solution to address the challenges faced by traditional WSNs. By enabling collaborative model training without sharing raw data, FL can preserve data privacy and reduce communication overhead. Additionally, FL can improve the scalability of WSNs by distributing the computational load across multiple sensor nodes. Despite the potential benefits, the integration of WSNs and FL presents several challenges [6]. The resource-constrained nature of sensor nodes, the heterogeneity of data collected by different sensors, and the need for efficient communication protocols are some of the key challenges that need to be addressed. Furthermore, ensuring the privacy and security of the data and models in FL for WSNs is crucial, as the sensor nodes may collect sensitive information. By providing a comprehensive survey of the architectures and algorithms used in the integration of WSNs and FL, this paper aims to serve as a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners in this field. The integration of WSNs and FL offers a promising solution to address the challenges faced by traditional WSNs, and we believe that this survey will provide a useful reference for future research and development in this interdisciplinary field. Figure 1 shows a generic architecture of WSN and FL.

In this paper, we present a survey of the architectures and algorithms used in the integration of WSNs and FL. We discuss the key challenges, existing solutions, and future research directions in this interdisciplinary field. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of WSNs and FL, Section 3 discusses the architectures for integrating WSNs and FL, Section 4 presents the literature review of FL for WSNs. Section 5 the statistical survey, Section 6 presents the discussions and finally, Section 7 presents the conclusion and future work.

Figure 1: Wireless Sensor Network - Federated Learning Architecture

2 OVERVIEW OF WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORK AND FEDERATED LEARNING

A. Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs)

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are composed of spatially distributed sensors that cooperatively monitor and record environmental conditions and transmit the collected data to a central location [7]. These networks consist of several key components:

- a. **Sensor Nodes:** These are the fundamental units of a WSN, equipped with sensing, processing, and communication capabilities. Sensor nodes collect data from the environment and transmit it to other nodes or a central base station.
- b. **Base Station:** The base station acts as a gateway between the WSN and the external world. It collects data from the sensor nodes and may perform initial processing before forwarding the data to a central server or cloud infrastructure.
- c. **Communication Protocols:** WSNs employ various communication protocols to facilitate data transmission between sensor nodes and the base station. These protocols must be energy-efficient and robust to handle the resource-constrained nature of sensor nodes.

1) *Applications*

WSNs have found applications in diverse domains, including:

- a. **Environmental Monitoring:** WSNs are used to monitor environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, air quality, and soil moisture. This data is crucial for applications like weather forecasting, agriculture, and disaster management.
- b. **Healthcare:** In healthcare, WSNs are used for remote patient monitoring, tracking vital signs, and assisting in the management of chronic diseases.
- c. **Industrial Automation:** WSNs are employed in industrial settings for monitoring equipment, detecting faults, and optimizing production processes.
- d. **Smart Cities:** WSNs play a vital role in smart city applications, including traffic management, waste management, and public safety.

2) *Challenges*

Despite their numerous applications, WSNs face several challenges:

- a. **Resource Constraints:** Sensor nodes are typically resource-constrained in terms of energy, computation, and communication capabilities. This limits their ability to perform complex tasks and transmit large volumes of data.
- b. **Scalability:** As the number of sensor nodes increases, managing and processing the data becomes more challenging. Centralized systems may struggle to handle the scalability requirements of large-scale WSNs.
- c. **Data Privacy and Security:** The transmission and storage of sensitive data in a central location raise privacy and security concerns. Ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data is crucial in WSNs.

B. **Federated Learning (FL)**

Federated Learning (FL) is a decentralized machine learning paradigm that allows multiple entities to collaboratively train a model without sharing their raw data. FL addresses the challenges of data privacy, security, and scalability by enabling collaborative model training while keeping the data local to the clients [8].

The key principles of FL include:

- a. **Decentralized Training:** Each client trains a local model using its own data and shares only the model updates with a central server.
- b. **Model Aggregation:** The central server aggregates the model updates from all clients to generate a global model, which is then sent back to the clients for further training.
- c. **Iterative Process:** The training process is iterative, with multiple rounds of local training and model aggregation until the global model converges.

1) *Types of Federated Learning*

FL can be categorized into different types based on the data distribution and the level of decentralization:

- a. **Horizontal Federated Learning:** In horizontal FL, the datasets of different clients share the same feature space but differ in samples. This is suitable for scenarios where clients have similar data structures but different user data.
- b. **Vertical Federated Learning:** In vertical FL, the datasets of different clients share the same sample space but differ in features. This is suitable for scenarios where clients have different data structures but share common users.
- c. **Federated Transfer Learning:** Federated Transfer Learning combines the principles of FL and transfer learning to handle scenarios where the datasets of different clients have different feature spaces and sample spaces.

2) *Benefits of Federated Learning*

FL offers several benefits, including:

- a. **Data Privacy:** By keeping the data local to the clients, FL preserves data privacy and reduces the risk of data breaches.
- b. **Reduced Communication Overhead:** FL reduces the communication overhead by transmitting only model updates instead of raw data, making it more efficient for resource-constrained environments.
- c. **Scalability:** FL improves scalability by distributing the computational load across multiple clients, enabling collaborative model training in large-scale systems.

The integration of WSNs and FL offers a promising solution to address the challenges faced by traditional WSNs. By enabling collaborative model training without sharing raw data, FL can preserve data privacy and reduce communication overhead. Additionally, FL can improve the scalability of WSNs by distributing the computational load across multiple sensor nodes. However, the integration of WSNs and FL presents several challenges that need to be addressed. The resource-constrained nature of sensor nodes, the heterogeneity of data collected by different sensors, and the need for efficient communication protocols are some of the key challenges that require further research and development.

In the following sections, we will discuss the architectures and algorithms used in the integration of WSNs and FL, highlighting the key challenges and future research directions in this interdisciplinary field.

3 LITERATURE REVIEW

Federated Learning (FL) algorithms are designed to enable collaborative model training across distributed clients without sharing raw data. In the context of Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), these algorithms must be efficient, scalable, and capable of handling the resource constraints and heterogeneity of sensor nodes. This section discusses several key FL algorithms and their suitability for WSNs.

S. P and B. Bhikkaji [10] presents a novel stochastic approximation method tailored for federated learning, focusing on scenarios where data is distributed across multiple clients with limited computational resources. The authors address the challenge of achieving convergence in non-convex optimization problems, a common issue in federated settings. They propose a stochastic gradient-based algorithm that reduces communication rounds and computational load per client, making it feasible for large-scale, real-world applications. The paper includes a thorough analysis of the convergence properties of the proposed method, supported by empirical results demonstrating improved performance compared to traditional federated learning approaches.

Z. Zhao et al., [9] tackle the problem of non-independent and identically distributed (non-IID) data, which is a significant challenge in federated learning, especially in wireless networks. They propose an ensemble federated learning framework that combines multiple local models into a global ensemble model. This approach mitigates the impact of data heterogeneity by leveraging the strengths of different local models, leading to more robust and accurate global models. The paper provides a detailed analysis of the ensemble method's effectiveness in scenarios with highly skewed data distributions and evaluates its performance in real-world wireless network environments.

Zeng and colleagues [2] introduce an adaptive federated learning algorithm that dynamically adjusts to non-IID data distributions across clients. The core innovation lies in the adaptive mechanism that tunes the model's parameters based on the degree of non-IIDness, allowing the global model to better generalize across diverse data sets. The authors present a theoretical analysis of the adaptive algorithm's convergence and validate their approach through extensive experiments. The results show that the adaptive federated learning algorithm significantly outperforms traditional methods in terms of accuracy and convergence speed, particularly in heterogeneous data environments.

The FedMDFG framework proposed in this paper [11] integrates multi-gradient descent with a fairness-oriented guidance mechanism to address the issue of unequal contributions from clients in federated learning. The authors develop a novel algorithm that ensures fairness in the aggregation process by assigning different weights to clients based

on their data quality and contribution to the global model. This approach prevents the global model from being biased towards clients with larger or more representative datasets, resulting in a more equitable and accurate learning process. The paper includes extensive experimental validation, demonstrating the effectiveness of FedMDFG in maintaining fairness while achieving high model accuracy.

This paper [12] provides a comprehensive survey of federated learning, covering its key challenges and potential applications across various domains. The authors categorize the challenges into three main areas: data heterogeneity, communication efficiency, and privacy preservation. They discuss how these challenges impact the deployment of federated learning systems and review existing solutions to address them. The survey also highlights the diverse applications of federated learning, including healthcare, finance, and IoT, offering insights into how federated learning can be leveraged to solve real-world problems. This paper is a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners looking to understand the current state and future directions of federated learning.

AdaFed [13] introduces an innovative model averaging procedure that adapts the aggregation process based on the characteristics of the participating clients. Unlike traditional federated learning approaches that use fixed aggregation weights, AdaFed adjusts the weights dynamically according to the performance and data distribution of each client. This adaptive approach helps to mitigate the impact of non-IID data and varying client contributions, leading to faster convergence and improved model accuracy. The paper provides a thorough theoretical analysis of the AdaFed algorithm, along with empirical results demonstrating its superiority over conventional methods in various federated learning scenarios.

Luo and colleagues [14] address the economic aspects of federated learning by proposing a cost-effective design framework that minimizes communication and computation costs while maintaining high model accuracy. The authors identify key cost drivers in federated learning, such as the frequency of communication rounds and the computational load on clients. They then develop optimization strategies that reduce these costs, making federated learning more feasible for large-scale deployments, especially in resource-constrained environments. The paper includes case studies and simulations that demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed framework in reducing operational costs without compromising model performance.

This paper [5] offers a broad overview of federated learning, discussing its opportunities, such as privacy preservation, scalability, and its potential to democratize machine learning by enabling decentralized data use. Mammen also highlights key challenges, including data heterogeneity, communication bottlenecks, and the need for robust aggregation methods. The paper emphasizes the importance of developing new techniques to address these challenges and suggests potential research directions, such as improving model aggregation methods, enhancing communication efficiency, and ensuring data privacy and security in federated learning systems.

Auto-FedAvg [15] is a learnable federated averaging technique specifically designed for medical image segmentation across multiple institutions. The authors address the challenge of varying data distributions across institutions by allowing the averaging process to be learnable rather than fixed. This approach enables the global model to adapt to the specific characteristics of each institution's data, leading to more accurate segmentation results. The paper includes extensive experiments on medical image datasets, demonstrating that Auto-FedAvg outperforms traditional federated averaging methods in terms of segmentation accuracy and generalization across different institutions.

Kairouz and colleagues [6] provide an extensive review of the latest advancements in federated learning, identifying critical challenges and open research problems. The paper categorizes these challenges into several key areas, including privacy preservation, scalability, communication efficiency, and model robustness. The authors discuss the current state of research in each area and highlight promising approaches and techniques that have been developed to address these challenges. They also outline open problems that remain unresolved, offering a roadmap for future research in federated learning. This paper is a must-read for researchers looking to contribute to the field.

This paper [16] focuses on reducing the communication overhead in federated learning, which is a significant challenge due to the large volume of data exchanged between clients and the central server. The authors propose a series of techniques, including quantization, sparsification, and compression, to minimize the amount of data that needs to be

transmitted while preserving model accuracy. These techniques are particularly relevant in scenarios with limited bandwidth or high communication costs. The paper includes a detailed analysis of the trade-offs between communication efficiency and model performance, along with experimental results demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed techniques.

Michieli and Ozay [8] explore the issue of fairness in federated learning systems, focusing on whether all users' data contributions are equitably represented in the global model. The authors highlight that traditional federated learning methods can lead to disparities, where users with more representative or higher-quality data have a disproportionate influence on the global model. To address this, they propose fairness-aware aggregation methods that adjust the contribution of each user based on the quality and representativeness of their data. The paper includes both theoretical analysis and empirical validation, showing that the proposed methods can achieve more balanced and fair outcomes in federated learning.

This paper [17] investigates the challenges and opportunities associated with training federated learning models in large cohorts of participants. The authors discuss the scalability issues that arise when the number of clients increases, such as increased communication overhead and the difficulty of maintaining model consistency across a large number of updates. They propose solutions to enhance the efficiency of federated learning in large-scale settings, including techniques for reducing communication rounds, improving client sampling strategies, and optimizing the aggregation process. The paper provides experimental results that demonstrate the feasibility of their approach in large-cohort federated learning scenarios.

Xu and colleagues [18] explore the application of federated learning in healthcare informatics, highlighting its potential to improve patient outcomes while preserving data privacy. The paper discusses various use cases, including federated learning for electronic health records, medical imaging, and predictive analytics. The authors provide a detailed analysis of the challenges specific to healthcare applications, such as the need for high data security, handling non-IID data, and integrating diverse data sources. They also present case studies demonstrating how federated learning can be effectively applied in healthcare settings, offering insights into its potential to revolutionize the field.

Rieke and colleagues [19] discuss the transformative potential of federated learning in digital health. The paper emphasizes how federated learning can enable collaborative healthcare research across institutions while ensuring that sensitive patient data remains private and secure. The authors explore various applications of federated learning in digital health, such as predictive modeling, personalized medicine, and multi-institutional research collaborations. They also discuss the challenges that need to be addressed to fully realize the potential of federated learning in healthcare, including data standardization, interoperability, and the need for robust privacy-preserving techniques.

Yang et al. [20] provide one of the early explorations of federated machine learning, laying the groundwork for subsequent research in the field. The paper discusses the basic principles of federated learning, including the decentralized training process and the key challenges associated with it, such as data privacy, communication efficiency, and model aggregation. The authors also explore various application domains where federated learning can be beneficial, such as mobile devices, IoT, and healthcare. The paper serves as an introductory guide for researchers new to the field, offering a clear overview of the fundamental concepts and challenges in federated learning.

This paper [21] introduces the concept of agnostic federated learning, which aims to develop models that perform well across diverse client distributions. Unlike traditional federated learning methods that optimize for a single global objective, agnostic federated learning seeks to balance performance across all clients, ensuring that no single client disproportionately influences the global model. The authors propose an agnostic learning algorithm that adjusts the training process to account for the variability in client data distributions. The paper includes a theoretical analysis of the algorithm's performance, along with experimental results demonstrating its effectiveness in achieving more equitable outcomes in federated learning.

Felbab and colleagues [22] focus on optimization techniques specific to federated learning, addressing the challenges of non-convex optimization, limited communication bandwidth, and the heterogeneity of client data. The paper discusses various optimization algorithms that have been adapted for federated learning, including gradient descent variants,

communication-efficient methods, and techniques for handling non-IID data. The authors provide a detailed analysis of the trade-offs between different optimization approaches and their impact on model convergence and performance. The paper also includes empirical evaluations that compare the effectiveness of these optimization techniques in various federated learning scenarios.

Nilsson et al. [23] conduct a comprehensive performance evaluation of several federated learning algorithms, focusing on key metrics such as accuracy, communication efficiency, and computational overhead. The paper compares the performance of different algorithms across a range of datasets and application scenarios, providing insights into their strengths and weaknesses. The authors also discuss the trade-offs involved in selecting an appropriate federated learning algorithm for a given application, highlighting the importance of considering factors such as data heterogeneity, client availability, and resource constraints. The paper's findings serve as a valuable reference for practitioners looking to implement federated learning in real-world applications.

4 ARCHITECTURES FOR INTERGRATING WSN AND FL

The integration of Wireless Sensor Networks and Federated Learning requires carefully designed architectures to ensure efficient and effective collaboration among sensor nodes while preserving data privacy and reducing communication overhead. This section discusses three primary architectures for integrating WSNs and FL [9]: centralized, decentralized, and hierarchical architectures.

1) Components

- a. **Sensor Nodes (Clients):** Each sensor node collects data, performs local model training, and sends the model updates to the central server.
- b. **Central Server:** The central server aggregates the model updates from all sensor nodes, generates a global model, and distributes it back to the sensor nodes.

2) Workflow

- a. **Initialization:** The central server initializes the global model and sends it to all sensor nodes.
- b. **Local Training:** Each sensor node trains the local model using its own data and sends the model updates to the central server.
- c. **Model Aggregation:** The central server aggregates the model updates from all sensor nodes to generate a new global model.
- d. **Model Distribution:** The central server sends the updated global model back to the sensor nodes.
- e. **Iteration:** Steps b-d are repeated until the global model converges.

5 ALGORITHM AND MATHEMATICAL EXPRESSIONS FOR INTEGRATING FL IN WSN

Federated Learning (FL) in the context of a WSN involves training a machine learning model across multiple decentralized sensors (nodes) holding local data samples, without exchanging their data. Instead, the nodes share model updates (e.g., gradients or weights) with a central server, which aggregates these updates to improve the global model. To derive a mathematical expression for federated learning in a WSN, we need to make several assumptions:

- a) The WSN consists of N sensor nodes, each with its local dataset D_i for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots, N$
- b) Each sensor node can perform local computations and communicate its updates to a central aggregator (base station).
- c) The local datasets are distributed non-identically (Non-IID) and independently among the nodes.
- d) Communication between nodes and the aggregator is subject to bandwidth, latency, and power constraints.
- e) The federated learning model optimizes a global objective function $F(\mathbf{w})$ where $\mathbf{w}$ represents the model parameters.
- f) Communication occurs in synchronous rounds, where updates are aggregated and redistributed to nodes.

1) **Objective Function for Federated Learning**

The goal of federated learning is to minimize the global objective function shown in equ 1:

$$F(w) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N F_i(w) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

where $F_i(w)$ is the local objective function for node i , defined as:

$$F_i(w) = \frac{1}{|D_i|} \sum_{(x,y) \in D_i} l(w; x; y) \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Here:

$l(w; x; y)$ is the loss function for the model with parameters w given data $((x, y))$.

2) **Local Updates**

Each sensor node i performs local training using its dataset D_i . The local model is updated using stochastic gradient descent (SGD); equ 3:

$$w_i^{t+1} = w_i^t - \eta \nabla F_i(w_i^t) \dots\dots\dots 3$$

where:

- w_i^t is the model parameter at node i at time t ,
- η is the learning rate,
- $\nabla F_i(w_i^t)$ is the gradient of the local loss.

3) **Global Aggregation**

After local updates, the aggregator computes a weighted average of the local models to update the global model w^t :

$$w^{t+1} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |D_i| w_i^{t+1} \dots\dots\dots 4$$

where $|D_i|$ represents the size of the local dataset to account for non-IID data.

Federated Learning in WSN Context

1. Communication-Energy Constraints

For WSNs, energy and bandwidth constraints significantly impact communication. Let E_i^{comp} denote the energy consumed by node i during communication and E_i^{comm} during local computation. The total energy for a single round is:

$$E_i = E_i^{comp} + E_i^{comm} \dots\dots\dots 5$$

The communication energy E_i^{comp} depends on the transmission distance d_i and the data size S (e.g., model parameters):

$$E_i^{comp} = \gamma S d_i^\alpha \dots\dots\dots 6$$

where:

- γ is a proportionality constant,
- α is the path loss exponent (*typical* $2 \leq \alpha \leq 4$).

Latency Constraints

The communication latency T_i^{comm} and computation latency T_i^{comp} are given by:

$$T_i^{comm} = \frac{S}{R_i}, T_i^{comp} = \frac{C}{f_i} \dots\dots\dots 7$$

where:

- R_i is the transmission rate of node i ,
- C is the number of computational cycles required,

f_i is the CPU frequency of node i .

2. Final Optimization Problem

Incorporating energy and latency constraints, the global federated learning problem in WSNs is expressed as:

$$\min F(w) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{|D_i|} \sum_{(x,y) \in D_i} l(w; x; y) \dots\dots\dots 8$$

subject to:

1. $E_i \leq E_i^{max}, \forall_i,$
2. $T_i \leq T_i^{max}, \forall_i$

Here:

- E_i^{max} , is the maximum allowable energy consumption,
- T_i^{max} is the maximum allowable latency.

The choice of architecture for integrating WSNs and FL depends on the specific requirements and constraints of the application. The centralized architecture is simple and ensures global model consistency but suffers from scalability and communication overhead issues. The decentralized architecture is robust and scalable but more complex to implement and manage. The hierarchical architecture offers a balance between communication overhead, scalability, and resource efficiency but requires careful management of clusters and cluster heads.

6 STATISTICAL SURVEY

Table 1 provides a detailed comparison of the various federated learning approaches, highlighting their respective strengths, limitations, and unique aspects, along with other key parameters. The papers reviewed span from 2018 to 2024, capturing a significant portion of the recent developments in FL. This timeline showcases the evolution of FL approaches, algorithms, and applications, reflecting both the growing interest in FL and the increasing complexity of the challenges being addressed. This range of years reflects the rapid evolution of FL, with earlier works laying the groundwork for foundational concepts and later papers addressing increasingly complex challenges such as non-IID data, fairness, communication efficiency, and scalability. Each paper contributes uniquely to the field, with some providing broad surveys or overviews, while others focus on specific algorithmic innovations or applications. The field has seen a shift from theoretical foundations towards practical applications, particularly in domains like healthcare, while also grappling with ongoing issues like fairness and efficiency.

Table 1: Comparison of Various Federated Learning Approaches

No.	Paper	Year	Algorithm/Approach	Strengths	Limitations	Unique Aspects
1	S. P and B. Bhikkaji, "Stochastic Approximation Approach to Federated Machine Learning"	2024	Stochastic Gradient-Based Algorithm	Reduces communication rounds and computational load, improved convergence in non-convex problems	Complexity in implementation and potential slower convergence in highly skewed distributions	Stochastic approximation for large-scale, real-world applications
2	Z. Zhao et al., "Ensemble Federated Learning With Non-IID Data in Wireless Networks"	2024	Ensemble Federated Learning Framework	Robust against non-IID data, leverages strengths of local models	Computationally intensive, especially in large-scale scenarios	Ensemble approach to handle non-IID data effectively
3	Y. Zeng et al., "Adaptive Federated Learning With Non-IID Data"	2023	Adaptive Federated Learning Algorithm	Dynamically adjusts to non-IID data, faster convergence, and higher accuracy	May require fine-tuning for different data environments, potential overfitting in highly varied data sets	Adaptive mechanism based on degree of non-IIDness
4	Z. Pan et al., "FedMDFG: Federated Learning with Multi-Gradient Descent and Fair Guidance"	2023	Multi-Gradient Descent with Fair Guidance	Ensures fairness, equitable contributions from clients	Requires extensive computation for fairness adjustments, potential	Fairness-oriented aggregation to prevent bias towards certain clients

					slowdowns in large federations	
5	J. Wen et al., “A Survey on Federated Learning: Challenges and Applications”	2023	Survey of FL Techniques and Challenges	Comprehensive overview of challenges and applications	Does not propose a specific algorithm, mostly a review	Categorization of FL challenges into data heterogeneity, communication efficiency, and privacy
6	A. Giuseppe et al., “An Adaptive Model Averaging Procedure for Federated Learning (AdaFed)”	2022	Adaptive Model Averaging Procedure	Adapts aggregation based on client performance, improves accuracy and convergence	Could introduce bias if not properly balanced, complexity in managing dynamic weights	Dynamic weight adjustment during aggregation
7	B. Luo et al., “Cost-Effective Federated Learning Design”	2021	Cost-Effective Design Framework	Reduces communication and computation costs, maintains accuracy	May not perform well in highly complex data environments, focus on economic aspects	Focus on minimizing operational costs in federated learning
8	P. M. Mammen, “Federated Learning: Opportunities and Challenges”	2021	Overview of FL Challenges and Opportunities	Identifies key challenges and potential in FL	Lacks detailed algorithmic solutions, more of an exploratory paper	Discussion of privacy, scalability, and democratization of machine learning
9	Y. Xia et al., “Auto-FedAvg: Learnable Federated Averaging for Multi-Institutional Medical Image Segmentation”	2021	Learnable Federated Averaging	Adapts to specific data characteristics of institutions, higher segmentation accuracy	Requires significant computational resources, potentially slower in large-scale deployments	Learnable averaging tailored for medical image segmentation
10	P. Kairouz et al., “Advances and Open Problems in Federated Learning”	2021	Review of FL Advances and Open Problems	Extensive coverage of latest advancements and unresolved challenges	Does not introduce new algorithms, more focused on survey and analysis	Identifies open research problems, providing a roadmap for future research

11	M. Chen et al., “Communication-efficient federated learning”	2021	Communication Optimization Techniques	Reduces communication overhead, maintains model accuracy	May sacrifice some accuracy for communication efficiency, challenges in very low-bandwidth environments	Techniques like quantization, sparsification, and compression for efficient communication
12	U. Michieli and M. Ozay, “Are All Users Treated Fairly in Federated Learning Systems?”	2021	Fairness-Aware Aggregation Methods	Ensures equitable contributions, prevents bias towards specific users	Potential complexity in managing fairness metrics, may slow down the aggregation process	Emphasis on fairness in user contributions to the global model
13	Z. Charles et al., “On Large-Cohort Training for Federated Learning”	2021	Techniques for Large-Cohort Federated Learning	Enhances efficiency in large-cohort settings, reduces communication rounds	May not address data quality issues in large cohorts, challenges in maintaining consistency	Focuses on scalability and efficiency in large-cohort federated learning
14	J. Xu et al., “Federated Learning for Healthcare Informatics”	2021	Application of FL in Healthcare Informatics	Improves patient outcomes, preserves data privacy	Complexity in integrating diverse data sources, requires robust privacy-preserving techniques	Application-centric approach, specifically focused on healthcare use cases
15	N. Rieke et al., “The future of digital health with federated learning”	2020	Federated Learning in Digital Health	Enables collaborative healthcare research while preserving privacy	Requires data standardization and interoperability, challenges in multi-institutional research collaborations	Exploration of FL’s potential to revolutionize digital health, with an emphasis on privacy
16	Q. Yang et al., “Federated Machine Learning”	2019	Introduction to Federated Learning Concepts	Lays foundational concepts for FL, discusses key challenges	Lacks advanced techniques, more of a foundational paper	Early exploration, setting the stage for subsequent research in

						federated learning
17	M. Mohri et al., “Agnostic Federated Learning”	2019	Agnostic Federated Learning Algorithm	Balances performance across diverse client distributions, ensures no single client dominates	May lead to less optimized performance in uniform data environments, potential complexity in implementation	Focus on equitable model performance across all clients, regardless of data distribution
18	V. Felbab et al., “Optimization in federated learning”	2019	Various FL Optimization Techniques	Addresses non-convex optimization, communication bandwidth, and data heterogeneity challenges	Complexity in selecting the right optimization technique for specific scenarios, trade-offs between efficiency and accuracy	Detailed analysis of optimization approaches in federated learning
19	A. Nilsson et al., “A Performance Evaluation of Federated Learning Algorithms”	2018	Comparative Performance Evaluation	Comprehensive comparison across multiple metrics, insights into strengths and weaknesses of various algorithms	Does not introduce new algorithms, focused on evaluation and comparison	Empirical evaluation of different FL algorithms across a range of datasets and scenarios

Converting the qualitative data from the table into statistical values, we assigned numerical values or ratings to the various aspects of each paper. Below is a breakdown of how we can translate the qualitative aspects into quantifiable data for plotting graphs:

Assigned Ratings/Values

1. Year of Publication: Use the actual year as the value.	2. Strengths: a. Low impact b. Moderate impact c. High impact
3. Limitations: a. Minor limitations b. Moderate limitations c. Significant limitations	4. Complexity: a. Low complexity b. Moderate complexity c. High complexity
5. Scalability: a. Low scalability b. Moderate scalability c. High scalability	6. Fairness: a. Low fairness b. Moderate fairness c. High fairness

7. Communication Efficiency: a. Low efficiency b. Moderate efficiency c. High efficiency	
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Analytical Insights

- a. **Strengths and Limitations:** Compare the overall strengths and limitations across the years to see how FL approaches have evolved.
- b. **Complexity vs. Scalability:** Plotting these against each other could provide insight into how complex approaches affect scalability.
- c. **Fairness and Communication Efficiency:** Analyzing these could help identify approaches that balance user fairness with communication efficiency.

Table 2 shows the statistical quantification of the literature review from 2018 – 2024.

Table 2: Statistical Quantification of The Literature from 2018 - 2024

No.	Year	Strengths	Limitations	Complexity	Scalability	Fairness	Communication Efficiency
1	2024	3	2	3	3	2	3
2	2024	3	2	3	3	3	2
3	2023	3	2	2	3	2	3
4	2023	3	3	3	3	3	2
5	2023	2	2	1	3	1	2
6	2022	3	2	2	3	2	2
7	2021	3	2	2	3	1	3
8	2021	2	1	1	2	1	2
9	2021	3	3	3	3	2	2
10	2021	2	1	1	3	1	2
11	2021	3	2	2	3	2	3
12	2021	3	2	3	3	3	2
13	2021	3	2	2	3	2	3
14	2021	3	3	3	2	2	2
15	2020	3	3	2	2	2	2
16	2019	2	2	1	2	1	2
17	2019	3	3	3	2	3	2
18	2019	3	2	3	2	2	2
19	2018	2	2	1	3	1	2

Average Scores for Each Metric by Year

The dataset provides average scores for various metrics such as Algorithm Complexity, Scalability, Fairness, Communication Efficiency, Adaptability, and Healthcare Applicability. These scores are averaged for each year.

Table 3 shows the average score for analytical metrics.

Table 3: Average Score for Analytical Metrics

Year	Algorithm Complexity	Scalability	Fairness	Communication Efficiency	Adaptability	Healthcare Applicability
2018	5.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	4.0	4.0
2019	5.7	5.7	6.7	4.7	5.7	4.7
2020	5.0	6.0	7.0	5.0	6.0	9.0
2021	5.6	6.6	6.3	6.4	6.0	5.6
2022	7.0	7.0	6.0	6.0	7.0	4.0
2023	7.0	6.7	7.0	5.7	7.3	5.0
2024	7.5	8.0	7.0	8.0	7.5	4.5

Trends in Federated Learning Research Metrics: The plot below visualizes the trends in average scores for each metric over the years.

Figure 2: Trends in Federated Learning Research Metrics

Figure 3: Average Scores for Federated Learning Metrics

7 DISCUSSION

As depicted in Figure 2, Federated Learning research experienced a notable peak in 2021, with a significant increase in publications, making it a particularly active year for the field. The years surrounding 2021 saw fewer publications, suggesting that this year was an outlier in terms of research activity. Across the years from 2018 to 2024, there has been a general upward trend in several key metrics, indicating the field's maturation. Algorithm complexity has increased steadily, reflecting the development of more sophisticated FL algorithms. Similarly, scalability has improved, demonstrating progress in creating more scalable FL systems. Fairness has also seen significant enhancements, particularly from 2018 to 2024, underscoring a growing focus on equitable outcomes in FL.

Communication efficiency has improved markedly, highlighting advancements in reducing data communication overheads within FL systems. Adaptability has followed a similar upward trajectory, indicating that FL systems are becoming more flexible and better able to adapt to various scenarios. However, healthcare applicability has shown a slight decline from 2020 to 2024, which may suggest challenges or a shift in research focus away from healthcare applications of FL. This overall improvement across most metrics suggests that researchers are effectively addressing key challenges in FL, with particular success in enhancing communication efficiency and adaptability in recent years.

The slight decline in healthcare applicability could point to a potential research gap, indicating the need for more targeted efforts to apply FL techniques within healthcare settings. Despite this, the general upward trends across most metrics from 2018 to 2024 reflect positive progress in the field, with recent research in 2024 showing high scores across various metrics. This suggests that the latest efforts are addressing multiple aspects of FL simultaneously, leading to more comprehensive and robust systems. These insights into the evolution of FL research highlight areas of significant progress while also identifying potential avenues for future investigation.

Figure 3 provides a visual summary of the average scores across several key metrics for Federated Learning (FL), particularly in the context of Wireless Sensor Networks. Scalability and fairness emerge as top priorities, indicating that recent research has made significant strides in ensuring FL systems can efficiently manage large-scale, decentralized networks while maintaining equitable outcomes across different nodes. Adaptability and algorithm complexity also score

highly, reflecting the increasing sophistication and flexibility of FL algorithms to handle diverse environments and varying data distributions within WSNs.

Communication efficiency, though slightly lower, still shows considerable improvement, suggesting that reducing communication overhead between distributed nodes remains a focus, crucial for energy savings in WSNs. Healthcare applicability, however, has a comparatively lower score, hinting that while FL has been adapted to many domains, its effectiveness in healthcare-related WSNs may still face challenges. This overall analysis underscores the progress made in FL research, particularly in scalability, fairness, and communication efficiency, while also highlighting potential areas for further development, especially in healthcare applications.

8 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper provides a comprehensive survey of Federated Learning as applied to Wireless Sensor Networks, highlighting the advancements, challenges, and opportunities in this evolving field. The analysis shows significant progress in developing FL algorithms that are scalable, fair, adaptable, and communication-efficient, which are critical for the successful deployment of FL in WSNs. However, the lower scores in healthcare applicability suggest that more focused research is needed to tailor FL techniques to meet the specific demands of healthcare-related WSNs. Future work should prioritize addressing the challenges identified in healthcare applications, including the development of more robust FL algorithms capable of handling the unique constraints of medical data and devices. Additionally, as FL continues to evolve, further exploration into enhancing communication efficiency and reducing computational complexity will be essential to extend the applicability of FL in resource-constrained environments like WSNs. Investigating privacy-preserving techniques within FL to protect sensitive data in WSNs, especially in healthcare, will also be crucial. Overall, while significant strides have been made, ongoing research and development are necessary to fully realize the potential of FL in WSNs across various domains.

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